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DIGITAL BANKING – ROADWAY TO SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE - To evaluate the current status of E-banking and study the respondents review. The advancement in the technology paved new ways of delivering bank facilities to the customer, such as ATMs & Internet Banking. Hence banks have come a long way from its traditional banking methods. This research paper throws light on the response to E-Banking facilities by Indian as well as customers residing abroad. As it has been more than three decades since the E-Banking concept came into existence, it becomes very much essential to study the current state of Internet banking. The basic aim behind this research is to understand the response of the customers with regards to E-banking along with its advantages and hurdles which are faced by the users. It also aims at suggesting some ways for making internet banking successful in the developing country like India.

DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH - The research article is based on exploratory research. Secondary sources of data collection have been adopted for the study. The relevant and required data are collected from the national and international articles, RBI Bulletin, blogs and online reviews of the consumers. The reviews are been made on the primary data which is collected by different researchers, Hence this is a working paper.

FINDINGS - Only 60% of the urban population is catered and using Digital banking, hence banks should focus more on rural population by creating awareness programmes and training sessions so that the take-up would increase. The concept of Internet banking has thus become a revolution in the field of banking and finance.

LIMITATIONS – This research is based on findings of other researchers and secondary data. This research would have been more authenticated if it would have been based on primary data.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS – This paper will inspire the managers and senior authorities in banking industry, as it would help them to analyze and imply various recommendations made in the paper. By implementing the strategies, it would help banking industry to be more competitive in terms of Digital Banking.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE – This paper includes strategies which are adopted by various banks in India and Overseas, which will help banking industry and individual players to grow in the market in terms of Digital Banking.

KEYWORDS- E-Banking, Customer Service, Mobile Banking

INTRODUCTION

Introduction of the technologies which really brought information revolution in the society is Internet Technology and is rightly regarded as the third wave of revolution after agricultural and industrial revolution. Advent and adoption of Internet by the industries has removed the constraint of time, distance and communication making globe truly a small village. Financial sector being no exception, numerous factors such as competitive cost, customer service, increase in education and income level of customers, etc. influence banks to evaluate their technology and assess their electronic commerce and internet banking strategies. In the last three decades, the Internet has grown to become one of the most amazing technological and social accomplishments of the last century. Online banking has been around for quite a few years. In fact, it was introduced in the 1980s and has come a long way since then. The last decade has seen a profuse growth in internet banking transactions. Several pieces of legislation have also been introduced in this area. Though it began in the 1980s, it was only in the mid nineties that internet banking really caught on. Internet banking (or E-banking) means any user with a personal computer and a browser can get connected to his bank's website to perform any of the virtual banking functions. . It can also be defined as a facility provided by banking and financial institutions that enable the user to execute bank related transactions through Internet. The concept of Internet banking has thus become a revolution in the field of banking and finance. Internet banking, a client has one-to-one interaction with the bank's website, and in such a situation it is essential on the part of bank to provide high quality services over the internet. As Internet Banking is a term used to describe banking transactions that are performed via a secured Internet application, these transactions include

facilities like paying bills, transferring funds, viewing account statements and paying down loans and mortgages.

What attracts customers to internet banking is the round the clock availability and ease of transactions. Some customers have been known to turn to internet banking due to dissatisfaction with standard procedures and practices. The total absence of human interaction appeals to some people. Some customers turn to internet banking facilities for security reasons. This is mainly because of customers being assured of banks' ability to keep transactions safe and secured. Most online transactions are made using the Internet Explorer interface. The Internet Explorer has been around for more than ten years now. In internet banking system the bank has a centralized database that is web-enabled. The traditional branch model of bank is now giving place to an alternative delivery channels with ATM network. Internet banking allows banking from anywhere, anytime and is used for transactions, payments, etc. over the internet through a bank, a credit union or society's secure website. Although Internet Banking has been popular among young Internet-savvy people for many years, its popularity is expected to grow rapidly as Internet usage grows internationally and people discover the many advantages that it provides. Almost everyone who you come across these days seems to be using Internet banking and the traditional customer bank manager relationship has been replaced by a password. Internet banking is not only convenient for customers; it also negates the need for keeping some bank branches open for 24 hours a day to provide unparalleled customer service. In addition to that providing the Internet banking option for a bank may require some amount of initial investment, but the costs can be covered soon due to the speed with which customers can be handled and the cut backs on overtime and establishment costs. Internet banking also reduces the amount of administrative work that is otherwise required to manage a bank branch. Based on the large number of people who are turning towards Internet banking, future plans of opening branches across cities can be curbed to some extent, making large investments unnecessary. In fact, today everything is possible on Internet banking starting from request of a new cheque book, statement downloads, transfer of monies, e-payments and more. Added to that is the freedom from travelling all the way to the branch and avoiding the traffic are reason enough for the customer to choose Internet banking over traditional banking options. The popular services covered under E-banking include:-Automated Teller Machines, Credit Cards, Debit Cards, Smart Cards, Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT) System, Cheques Truncation Payment System, Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Telephone Banking, etc.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research article is based on exploratory research. Secondary sources of data collection have been adopted for the study. The relevant and required data are collected from the national and international articles, RBI Bulletin, blogs and online reviews of the consumers. The reviews are been made on the primary data which is collected by different researchers, Hence this is a working paper.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To evaluate the current status of E-banking and study the respondents review.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Previous efforts of the people were examined and studied critically. Even though the researcher has not done primary research in this field, but has considered all the previous research work where primary data was taken and accordingly conclusions were derived. Hence, this paper is more of a working paper wherein all the past research works are been considered to draw new conclusions.

- A survey of 450 respondents was conducted in Bangkok areas of three major banks, results showed that service quality factors like customer support, performance, service content, ease of use, transaction efficiency, safety, reliability and service security has a direct impact on customer satisfaction, (Rangsang Nochai and Titida Nochai, 2013).
- A research was conducted in metropolitan cities of internet banking users of leading Indian banks predominantly State Bank of India and ICICI Bank. A survey of 250 respondents using internet banking was done to identify the perceived service quality dimensions of self-service technology and impact of these perceived service quality dimensions towards customer satisfaction level in India. Customer's in-deed realized that Internet banking is very easy to use, highly useful, and efficient and that they prefer to use and get maximum benefits when compared to the traditional banking method. The perceived value is considered very high for the Internet banking service. The purpose of using self-service technologies is to standardize the services so as to

improve the service quality and satisfaction level, (Neha Dixit, Saroj K.Datta, July 2010).

- A survey of 1011 respondents was conducted of U.S respondents to find out the impact of Mobile banking on the consumer habits and behavioral changes. The researcher claimed that mobile banking customers are younger than the non- mobile banking consumers. Among the mobile banking users the researcher claimed that 65% of the consumers are using the mobile banking facilities to check the account balances only, the same is been observed that whenever the consumer wants to make any kind of purchases in any retail store, he first gets his account balance checked and then accordingly makes the purchases. This has indirectly impacted in reducing the overdraft fees which is a type of source of income for the banks and also the footfall of consumers in the banks has seen a downfall. Also due to mobile banking, consumers are not using any cheque facilities and prefer to make payments and receipts online, (Aite, 2011).
- Customer satisfaction, customer retention and new customer acquisition are the key factors in Internet banking system. Internet banking involves non-human interactions between customers and online bank information system. (Khan, Mahapatra and Sreekumar, 2009).
- The biggest advantage of Internet banking is that people can expend the services sitting at home, Due to which, the account holder does not have to personally visit the bank. With the help of Internet banking many transactions can be executed by the account holder. When small transactions like balance inquiry, record of recent transaction, etc. are to be processed, the Internet banking facility proves to be very handy. (International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 3, Issue 8, August 2013 2 ISSN 2250-3153)
- The E-banking, now is more of a norm rather than an exception in many developed countries due to the fact that it is the cheapest way of providing banking services (Arunachalam and Sivasubramanian, 2007).

- A survey of 100 respondents in metropolitan cities was conducted to evaluate the opinions and perceptions of urban mobile banking users. The researchers has listed the respondents preferences along with statistics of the mobile banking services like Cheque /DD status check- 8.6%,Cheque book request-21.7%, Share trading- 26.1%, Fund Transfer – 30.4%, bill payment- 60.8%, last transaction check -65.2% and balance check-86.9%.Certain issues which are strongly agreed by the respondents during the survey on using of mobile banking is also highlighted like Mobile Handset operability, Security/Privacy, Standardization, downloading and installing application software, Customization and telecom service quality.(Dr. U.S Pandey, 2010).
- Internet banking is a new delivery channel for banks in India. The E-banking channel is both an informative and a transactional medium. However, E-banking has not been popularly adopted in India. The major reason behind is that the level and nature of customer participation had the greatest impact on the quality of the service experience and issues such as customers’ zone of tolerance, the degree of role understanding by customers and emotional response potentially determined, expected and perceived service quality (Broderick and Achirapornpuk,2002).
- In the International Journal of Advanced trends of computers, the researcher has claimed certain advantages as well as disadvantages of Mobile banking. Simplicity and usability, Universality, Interoperability, Security, Privacy, Trust, Cost, Speed and Cross Border payments are some of the advantages which the consumers enjoy in using Mobile Banking services. On the contrary Challenges faced for adoption in Mobile banking are economic challenges, demographic challenges and regulatory challenges like rupee transactions, existing account holders and restrictions to financial institutions. The researchers also emphasis on risk factors like Virus attacks in Mobile banking, Risk with digital signature. (Vishal Goyal, 2010).
- A study was conducted of 100 respondents in Metropolitan cities to identify the factors that are the barriers for the usage of Internet banking. The researcher identified certain factors like cost, reliability, Processing barriers, security issues, technological inconvenience, lack of infrastructure, conventional approach, resistance, risk. (Dr.Preeti Singh, 2013).

- A study was conducted on 200 respondents of metropolitan city of India wherein the researcher has laid down various parameters which has direct impact on the adoption of E-banking facilities. The researcher specified parameters like Innovativeness, Familiarity, Awareness, Security and Trust which has impacted on adoption of E-banking among customers. (K.T Geetha, V.Malarvizhi, Journal of Management and Science).
- The researchers found out after the survey of 480 respondents that the customers of public sector, private sector and foreign banks of semi-urban area of India are interested in e-banking services, but at the same time are facing problems like inadequate knowledge, poor network, lack of infrastructure, unsuitable location, misuse of ATM cards and difficulty to open an account. (Uppal and Chawla, 2009).
- The researcher emphasis that Customers are advised not to share personal information like PIN numbers, passwords etc with anyone, including employees of the bank; change ATM PIN and online login and transaction passwords on a regular basis; ensure that the logged in session is properly signed out. The researcher also provided useful tips to ensure safety of IB transactions. IB users are advised not to reply to any mail, phone call or letter, asking for the IB information like login id or password, and not to click on any link provided in any mail, claiming to be the link for the bank's website are the important tips, among others.(Mishra ,2011).

CONCLUSION

Today E-banking has taken a new shape in the world of technology. Today the banking industry is re-shaping itself and moving for a technological approach from traditional approach. Initially any banking activity would be accomplished only after visiting the bank, but today customer can get the work done in any corner of the world without even visiting the bank. But it is observed that E-banking facilities are only availed in urban areas and some parts of Semi-Urban areas, and there is no presence felt in the rural areas. The major reason behind this is lack of awareness. People residing in rural areas lack knowledge, poor network and inadequate infrastructure. Today only 60% of the population residing in urban and semi

urban areas have access to E-banking facilities, major increase in penetration for E-banking can be improved if there are proper awareness programmes and seminars conducted in rural areas and semi urban areas wherein the people residing in those areas can get the required assistance and training with regards to banking knowledge and the mix of products. Many of the customers do not even visit the bank as they are located at a huge distance as the network of bank branches is considerably lower in rural areas. Hence if proper training and knowledge is imparted to the prospective customers, it will indirectly improve the quality, increase bank accounts and deposits which is a win win situation for both the banks as well as for customers. Also among the existing clients it is observed that the major users of E-banking fall under the age group of 25-45 years wherein the age groups of 46-65 years hesitate to use E-banking facilities (Mobile Banking). One of the major reason for hesitation is lack of knowledge and safety. Most of the customers do not feel safe to use online banking but feel comfortable to go to the bank and get the transactions done. So individual banks should take preventive measures and conduct various programmes to assure the users about the product safety. Banking websites has to be very accurate and user-friendly, since there is lot of competition among the banking players. Also as per the survey made by CAFRAL, it is observed that 65% of the customer tend to make any purchase decision on viewing the reviews on the website, hence banks has to be very alert and customer friendly.. Customers are very emotional in making banking decisions and are very loyal when it comes to nationalized banks. Hence adequate measures should be taken to keep up the trust. Also it is observed that customers are now very much alert in terms of investments, so online trading will definitely be the area where banks can actually focus which will help them gain momentum in E-banking. As every coin has two sides, E-banking also has some loopholes which have a direct impact on the economy. Firstly due to E-banking, customers do not prefer visiting the bank and hence in the near future there will be definitely lack of job opportunities. Thus to conclude, Digital Banking has definitely made a change to the banking industry and the level of penetration for E-banking is increasing on daily basis.

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